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Beam Transfer Systems Feasibility Study input for FCC-ee

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Summary

This study explores the design and feasibility of the beam transfer systems for the Future Circular Collider (FCC-ee). It highlights the technical concepts, operational parameters, and challenges to achieve the required performance levels.

The transfer line design and hardware considerations from the injector complex are evaluated. An injection concept into the booster around the PA collider tunnel straight section is also discussed.

The collider's PB straight section is dedicated to the injection and extraction systems connecting the booster and the collider. This includes the beam dump systems, all required transfer lines from the booster to the collider, and the transfer lines towards the two dumps for both machines. The concept of top-up injection is also addressed.

The first design concepts and hardware systems have been selected, and future studies will focus on addressing the identified challenges.

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1 Fcc-ee collider

1.1 Injection - extraction

The technical straight section in point B (PB) of the FCC is dedicated to the beam transfer from the booster to the collider and to the dump systems. Figure 1 depicts the arrangement of the booster extraction, collider injection, collider dump and booster dump for the positron beam. The corresponding layout for the electron beam has a symmetrical design with respect to the positron beam. In total, 8 systems are installed in this area and this section focuses on the collider system and the top-up injection and dump concepts.

Figure 1: Layout of injection and extraction systems in the PB section with the IP at $z=0$. Real space beam trajectories in the horizontal plane for positrons are represented as coloured lines and the blue rectangles denote the location of kicker and septum magnets. The electron trajectories are symmetric about the IP and have been omitted here for clarity.

1.1.1 Top-up injection

The integrated and peak luminosity targets of the collider necessitate a continuous injection scheme from a full-energy booster, as the beam lifetime during collisions is well below 1 h. Due to the high bunch charge in the collider and the limitations of the injector complex, a swap-out scheme is not feasible; thus, a top-up injection scheme is required. Depending on the operation mode, the interval between injections of positron and electron beams ranges from 40 s to 10 s, the number of bunches per injection varies between 1120 and 56, and the maximum charge per bunch ranges from virtually zero to 2.14×10^{10} .

Among the four operation modes, the Z mode is particularly challenging, with approximately 18 MJ of stored beam energy per collider ring at an energy of 45.6 GeV. As such, the Z mode is the current focus of the injection scheme design. In this mode at each injection occurring every 3 s, up to 10% of the collider's maximum bunch intensity and up to 1120

bunches are injected totalling up to 1% of the collider nominal intensity. This is considered to be a reasonably safe intensity to be transferred from the booster to the collider, provided that a series of collimators is installed in the booster extraction region and also along the transfer line to the collider to intercept mis-kicked bunches.

Several possible schemes have been explored to implement top-up injection at the FCC-ee collider [1]. The longitudinal schemes, which require an individual kick to each injected bunch trailing circulating bunches, have been excluded due to complexity of the required kicker system. For the traditional off-axis injection scheme, the injected beam (beamlet) has a transverse horizontal betatron offset relative to the circulating beam at the injection point. The horizontal betatron oscillation of the beamlet results in a physical offset along the entire ring and in particular in the experimental insertions. The impact of the SR cone originating from the beamlet on the SR (Synchrotron Radiation) mask and aperture limitation around the experimental insertion was modelled and showed an unacceptable level [3].

On axis injection

For on-axis injection, the beam is placed onto the chromatic closed orbit, where the energy offset together with the ring's optics dispersion provides the horizontal separation between the injected and circulating beams. The beamlet undergoes synchrotron oscillations, and around IPs it overlaps with the circulating beam due to the zero dispersion, thus preventing any increase in the SR cones or of the experiment background.

The beamlet benefits from faster damping compared to off-axis injection since synchrotron oscillations damp twice as fast as betatron oscillations. In the Z operation mode, injections occur every 3 s while the synchrotron damping time is approximately 1200 turns (0.36 s). The on-axis injection provides more than 8 damping times between injections, which is sufficient for complete merging of the beamlet. Another advantage of on-axis injection was observed at the LEP collider, where this scheme provided higher efficiency and lower sensitivity to errors at the injection point [13]. Therefore, the conventional on-axis injection has been selected for the present baseline concept.

The distance between injected and circulating beams establishes the requirements on the energy offset and dispersion at the injection septum:

$$|D_x \Delta| = 5\sigma_{cir} + S + 5\sigma_{inj} \quad (1)$$

where D_x is the dispersion at the injection point, Δ is the relative energy offset of the injected beam, S is the blade thickness of the septum, σ_{cir} and σ_{inj} are the beam sizes of the circulating and injected beams at the injection point. The beam size is given by $\sigma = \sqrt{\beta \times \epsilon + (D_x \times \delta)^2}$, where ϵ represents the beam emittance, β is the beta function, and δ is the relative energy spread.

In order to understand the optics requirements of the lattice for various beam conditions and energy offsets, Eq. 1 is expanded with the following assumptions:

- The beta functions of the injected and circulating beams at the injection point are equal and denoted β_x .
- The dispersion of the injected beam is zero, hence $\sigma_{inj} = \sqrt{\beta_x \times \epsilon_{inj}}$

As a result:

$$D_x = \frac{(S + 5\sqrt{\epsilon_{inj}\beta_x})\Delta}{\Delta^2 - 25\delta_{cir}^2} + \frac{5\sqrt{\epsilon_{cir}\beta_x(\Delta^2 - 25\delta_{cir}^2)} + (S + 5\sqrt{\epsilon_{inj}\beta_x})^2\delta_{cir}^2}{\Delta^2 - 25\delta_{cir}^2} \quad (2)$$

where subscripts $_{cir}$ and $_{inj}$ respectively designate the circulating and injected beams' characteristics.

Figure 2: Optics requirements at the injection point with different septum blade thicknesses using the Z-mode emittances ($\epsilon_{cir} = 0.71$ nm and $\epsilon_{inj} = 0.12$ nm) and an energy offset of $\Delta = 0.95$ %.

For a given set of beam conditions, the requirements on the optics at the injection point can be visualised using Eq. 2. That relation between dispersion and beta function is shown in Fig. 2 for the Z mode beam characteristics. The choice of septa thicknesses covers a realistic range from 0.3 mm for electrostatic septa to 3 mm for a thin magnetic septum. For a given septa thickness, the monotonic dependence shows that a larger β_x , which leads to a larger beam size, must be offset by a larger dispersion to increase the physical separation between injected and circulating beams.

Conversely, at a fixed β_x , Fig. 2 shows a high sensitivity of the required dispersion to the thickness of the septum. An initial concept aimed at using an electrostatic septum for the baseline scheme, but there are significant uncertainties on the reliability of such a system in the presence of synchrotron radiation. Therefore, the present concept focuses on thin magnetic septa with $S = 2.8$ mm.

Injection bump

During injection the circulating beam closed orbit is placed at $5\sigma_{cir}$ from the septum blade (see Eq. 1). This condition must be fulfilled for the shortest possible duration because the septum, or a protection absorber placed immediately upstream, becomes the primary aperture of the ring. While the nominal collimation and dynamic aperture place the on-momentum acceptance between $5\sigma_{cir}$ and $15\sigma_{cir}$, a constant limit at $5\sigma_{cir}$ would considerably shorten the associated quantum lifetime [12]. Therefore, the baseline concept features a fast bump to bring the circulating beam close to the injection septum for one single turn. Two

sets of fast bumper magnets placed at a relative phase advance of π are used to produce the orbit bump with a height of $10\sigma_{inj} + S$ at the injection point.

The failure of one of the bumpers would cause an open oscillation of all circulating bunches, potentially resulting in significant losses at downstream machine aperture bottlenecks (i.e. ideally at the collimators). The number of bumpers has to be defined in order to keep the oscillation amplitude, in case of failure, remaining small enough to avoid major damage to the machine. Moreover, an absorber must be installed upstream of the septum blade to shield it from accidental and continuous losses. The absorber and the septum should never be the primary aperture bottleneck; this role should always remain with the collimators. The amplitude of the bump might need to be reviewed if this condition is not fulfilled.

Injection lattice

The collider ring baseline optics for technical straight sections have been optimised to include the on-axis injection requirements in its most recent V24.4_GHC [22]. This collider optics in the PB straight section is shown in Fig. 3 with the injection region on the right side of the IP and the crossing dipoles in the centre. The injection point is located at $s = 800$ m where it achieves a dispersion of $D_x = -1.5$ m and $\beta_x = 1000$ m. This allows on-axis injection with an energy offset of $\sim 1\%$, providing sufficient space for the magnetic septum blade of approximately 3 mm.

Figure 3: The collider optics in the PB straight section with the longitudinal position relative to the IP.

The circulating beam injection π -bump is shown in Fig. 3 with the circulating beam envelope reaching the inside edge of the injection septum. The injected beam approaches the injection septum from negative values of x , as the injection occurs from the inside of the ring. It then follows the chromatic closed orbit downstream of the septum. After one turn, the orbit bump is collapsed, allowing the beamlet can circulate until it merges with the main

circulating beam.

The required phase advance for this bump is fulfilled but the difference in beta function at the two locations requires using different kicker strengths at both stations. The hardware requirements for the baseline injection scheme are summarised in Tab. 1.

Table 1: Collider injection hardware requirements.

System	Value	unit
Beam energy	45.6 to 182.5	GeV
Thick septum apparent thickness	10	mm
Thick septum deflection	0.1	mrad
Thin septum apparent thickness	2.8	mm
Thin septum deflection	100	μ rad
Fast bump kicker angles	40 and 60	μ rad
Fast bump kicker max. rise/fall time	600	ns
Fast bump kicker flattop	304	μ s
Fast bump kicker maximum ripple	1.5	%

While the zero-dispersion condition was introduced to simplify the solution of Eq. 1 and to reduce the size of the injected beam at the injection septum, it also causes a mismatch between injected and circulating beams. The distance of the injected beam from the septum is constrained by the energy offset. In the Z and W modes in particular, the lattice momentum acceptance limits the energy offset of the injected beam to approximately 1%. On the other hand, the dispersion mismatch causes betatron oscillations in the injected particles away from the chromatic closed orbit. This effect remains moderate, as the momentum spread of the injected beam δ_{inj} is small compared to the energy offset. Additional studies will be needed to quantify this effect and investigate different matching for each operation mode.

For the transfer from the booster to the collider, a complete design of the line will need to be developed. Presently, this line is approximately 450 m long from the booster extraction at the centre of the straight section to the collider injection point (see Fig. 8). Since the booster ring is 1030 mm above the collider plane, particular attention must be paid to preserving the small vertical emittance and precisely matching the vertical optics to the collider ring. In the horizontal plane, immediately upstream of the thin collider injection septum, a thicker magnetic septum is considered for the beam trajectory with specifications listed in Tab. 1.

Injection settings at each mode

Both booster and collider beam parameters depend on the operation mode. The collider beam parameters considered correspond to the predicted emittances and momentum spread during collision listed in [34]. For the booster, the beam parameters correspond to the equilibrium emittance of the lattice at the higher energy modes [18]. However, due to the limited time in the booster to reach the equilibrium emittance during the Z-mode cycle other values based on the booster cycling model and the injected beam characteristics are considered: $\epsilon_x = 0.12$ nm, $\epsilon_y = 10$ pm and $\delta = 0.38 \times 10^{-3}$, corresponding to the horizontal

emittance, vertical emittance, and momentum spread, respectively.

In the present concept, the lattice configuration of the injection straight section as well as the injection devices' specifications remains the same for all operation modes. With fixed optics and septum thickness, it is the energy offset that is optimised at every energy mode to adapt to the different beam characteristics and ring momentum acceptance. The baseline injection settings for the four operation modes are shown in Fig. 4.

In order to maintain a clearance of 5σ for both the injected and circulating beam a larger energy offset is required for modes with higher beam emittance (see Eq. 1), and the energy offset in H and $t\bar{t}$ mode is increased to 1.4% and 1.6%, respectively. This remains compatible with the large momentum acceptance in Higgs and $t\bar{t}$ modes, which are $\pm 1.6\%$ and $-2.8/+2.5\%$, respectively [34]. For Z mode, the RF acceptance is 1.06% and the momentum acceptance is approximately 1%, so the baseline injected beam energy offset is set to 0.95% to ensure the entire injected beam fits within the ring acceptance.

Figure 4: Normalised horizontal phase space at the collider injection point for each operation mode. Beam distributions and associated 5σ envelopes around the injection septum are shown for each mode.

The collider's and booster's equilibrium emittances in the W mode are significantly larger, but the energy acceptance of the ring is still limited to 1%. This prevents increasing the energy offset as in the higher energy modes and makes the on-axis scheme unable to provide sufficient clearance for the 2.8 mm septum blade. The baseline on-axis injection could still be

implemented by adapting the ring optics, increasing the ring dynamic aperture, optimising the injected beam Twiss parameters or reducing the clearance considered. However, each of those prospects must be investigated in detail, so the present concept instead proposes to introduce a small betatron offset to the scheme and moving towards a hybrid injection for the W mode. The purple dashed line in Fig. 4(b) represents the chromatic orbit for the energy offset considered, and the injected beam is further offset by 1 mm away from the septum, which corresponds to $0.5 \sigma_{\text{cir}}$.

Hybrid injection scheme

The hybrid injection scheme increases the separation between injected and circulating beams without increasing the energy offset, making it partially on-axis and off-axis. While the off-axis injection is not possible for the FCC collider, a small betatron oscillation is not incompatible with the SR absorption around the experimental IPs [3]. Other effects discussed earlier, such as experimental background sensitivity and errors, may still play a significant role and will need to be quantified.

Figure 5: Injection efficiency versus injected beam energy offset for the Z mode.

Presently, the injection efficiency is modelled using particle tracking of the injected beam in the collider ring lattice. The tracking consists of a Gaussian 6D distribution of 2500 injected particles, which are tracked for 3000 turns using the Xsuite code [24]. The synchrotron radiation model used accounts for quantum excitation to accurately predict the behaviour of particles injected near the edge of stability. This model does not include beam-beam interaction, collective effects or errors, which will need to be included for comprehensive simulations of the injection scheme.

The evolution of the simulated injection efficiency for on-axis and hybrid injection schemes

is shown in Fig.5. The energy offset of the baseline on-axis injection is SI0.95%, with an injection efficiency of 99%. This confirms the baseline injection scheme is achievable with the present lattice and the injected beam is within the acceptance of the ring.

At other injection offsets, only the energy of the injected beam is adjusted but the optics is not optimised and the physical beam position is unchanged. Below the baseline on-axis scheme energy offset, the injection efficiency remains high, which indicates that the DA and MA are sufficient to capture an injected beam with some betatron offset. At an energy offset below about 0.7% the injection efficiency decreases, which shows that a maximum betatron offset is reached and part of the injected beam is outside the lattice DA. Due to the energy acceptance of the lattice, of $\pm 1\%$, the injection efficiency drops quickly for energy offset above the baseline scheme.

Figure 6: Collider DA as a function of momentum for the Z mode with stable regions shown in white and the acceptance limits for different phases as blue lines [2]. The red dots show the injected beam betatron offset associated to lower energy offset. The stars mark the position of other injection simulations conducted at fixed momentum offset with increasing betatron offsets.

The hybrid injection scheme has to maintain a constant physical distance between injected and circulating beam at the injection point due to the septum thickness. While the optics remains unchanged this results in a geometrical condition in the DA-MA plane which is represented as red dots in Fig. 6. Above and to the right of this line, injection is physically possible but limited by DA and MA. Below and to the left of this line the injection is geometrically not possible.

In order to probe further the relation between injection efficiency and DA/MA, additional tracking at various betatron offsets was carried out. Figure 7 shows the evolution of injection efficiency for increasing betatron offset at constant energy offsets to explore other possible hybrid injection settings. The associated positions in the DA, with corresponding colours, are shown in Fig. 6. This shows a clear relation between the DA/MA and the simulated injection efficiency. While the baseline on-axis injection scheme is very close to the edge of

Figure 7: Injection efficiency versus betatron offset at two different energy offset for Z mode.

stability there is significant space to adjust the energy and betatron offsets, thanks to the injected beam being considerably smaller than the circulating one.

While the model used presently only includes synchrotron radiation and quantum excitation it shows a method to find and optimise injection settings and establishes the geometrical limit required for the injection septum with the present optics. Future modelling of lattice errors, beam-beam and other collective effects will need to be carried, but preserving DA/MA will remain critical to the feasibility of a top-up injection scheme.

1.1.2 Collider dump

The stored beam energy can reach 18 MJ per beam during Z mode operation, which is the highest stored energy among the lepton machines worldwide. Due to the synchrotron radiation damping, the beam sizes in the FCC-ee will be much smaller than in typical hadron machines, leading to a much higher energy density. The vertical beam size, in particular, is on the order of tens of micrometres, corresponding to energy densities around 5 GJ/mm², which cannot be absorbed safely [31]. The design and operation of the beam abort system have to account for such destructive potential and several safety levels have to be implemented to avoid damaging accelerator components in case of hardware failure. Protection elements, typically located at a precise phase advance from the extraction kickers, have to be installed to intercept any mis-kicked beam in case of a spurious firing of the kickers that is not synchronised with the abort gap. The voltage of the kickers, as well as the current of the septa and ring dipoles, must be constantly monitored to ensure they remain within tight thresholds relative to the reference value for a fixed energy.

A retriggering system, which fires all the remaining kickers in case of the spurious firing of one kicker, has to be envisaged and the reaction time defined based on the consequences of such an event. Redundancy in the powering scheme, the controls and interlock logic have to be implemented to ensure achieving the required level of reliability and availability of the

Figure 8: Optical function from the collider ring to the dump. The lower plot shows the physical position of the dump line relative to the collider.

system. The number of magnets has to be defined with the aim of reducing the maximum operational voltage and thus minimise the risk of spurious firing and the sensitivity to failures. Out of vacuum designs should be preferred to eliminate the risk of flashovers. The position of the beam at extraction has to be constantly monitored and the beam dumped before orbit drifts translate into losses at extraction above what can be considered a safe level (to be defined). Similar measures to the present LHC beam dump system will need to be considered, and adapted to the specificities of the FCC collider but presently no fundamental major obstacle have been identified.

The collider dump design is implemented at the entrance of the PB straight section and extracted outwards with the dump placed on the other side of the IP, as shown in Fig.1. The beam dump is located 5 m away from the ring to allow sufficient space for shielding and to limit radiation to the ring equipment [32]. The present geometry uses a small deflection angle to achieve the required separation and a long transport line of 1200 m from the ring extraction point.

In order to reduce the energy density on the dump, the present design aims for a large beta function and dispersion in both horizontal and vertical plane, to maximise the beam size. Despite the significant length of the line, the natural divergence of the beam at the extraction point is insufficient to produce a large enough beam spot on the dump. Therefore, a dedicated set of four quadrupole magnets is installed in the transfer line to further increase the beam divergence as shown in Fig. 8.

In the horizontal plane, the dump kicker and septa provide the deflection to reach the dump but also a significant dispersion that is further amplified by the dump line quadrupoles to reach 20 m at the dump. Along with the beta function of 121 448 m and the beam parameters in collision, the present design achieves a horizontal beam size on the dump of 10 mm for the Z mode.

However, the vertical emittance is several orders of magnitude smaller and even the

large vertical beta function of 56 000 km achieved at the dump is not sufficient to produce a sufficiently large beam. Therefore, a 1 mrad vertical dipole is placed at the start of the dedicated dump line to create a vertical dispersion that is further amplified by the dump line quadrupoles to reach 23 m at the dump. Between the betatron and dispersive contribution, this scheme also provides a large beam size in the vertical plane of 10 mm for the Z mode using the beam characteristics expected in collision. The vertical deflection also places the dumped beam at the height of the booster.

This design relies on both transverse emittance and energy spread to reach a large RMS beam size of 10 mm in each plane at the dump for the Z operation. The transverse emittances are given by the lattice and should not be significantly smaller than expected. The momentum spread, however, is significantly increased by the beam interaction and could be smaller if the collider is operated at lower luminosity. Therefore, the dump design will need to account for all possible beams and include considerations to handle beams with lower momentum spread that will reduce the dispersive contribution to the beam size on the dump.

Figure 9: Collider dump for the Z mode around the ring extraction point in the referential of the ring (a) and up to the dump in the referential of the dump line (b) with the horizontal scale referenced to the centre of the straight section. Dumped beam envelopes are shown in transparency for the two extreme cases of kicker strength variation of $\pm 20\%$ around their nominal value.

The extraction design follows a traditional fast extraction scheme in the horizontal plane (see Fig.9). The extraction kickers and septa are placed on either side of a defocusing quadrupole to increase the horizontal deflection angle while minimising the required kick strength. A horizontal bypass channel in the focusing quadrupole `qrfr2.1`, located downstream of the septa, is required to direct the extracted beam to the dump line.

The circulating beam is extracted in one turn so that the kicker flattop must be 304 μ s and its rise time should be smaller than the filling scheme abort gap of 0.6 μ s. The dump design hardware requirements are summarised in Tab. 2.

Another constraint to the design of the dump comes from machine protection considerations requiring a safe extraction of the beam in the event when one of the kicker modules

fails. Figure 9 shows that the dumped beam envelopes almost clears the septum aperture even assuming with a variations of $\pm 20\%$ on the overall kicker strength. Further studies are needed to confirm this capability with the hardware specifications presently considered at each operation mode. The horizontal phase advance between the extraction kicker and the dump is set close to π to minimise the influence of kicker angle on the beam position and maintain the 5σ beam envelope at the dump within ± 10 cm of the reference position.

This large acceptable variation in the kicker strength can be used to determine the fraction of kicker modules that could acceptably fail at the same time and to relax the flatness requirement on the kick flattop to potentially use less costly generator design. This requirement is simply listed as the kicker flatness in Tab. 2. However, the large design optical functions at the dump will require a careful analysis of possible error and failure cases to ensure that the beam can be safely channelled to the dump, for instance in case of a betatron offset of the circulating beam.

Table 2: Summary of the collider dump scheme hardware requirements

	Kicker	Septum
Beam energy (GeV)	45.6 to 182.5	
Deflection angle per system (mrad)	0.3	5
Maximum repetition frequency (Hz)	0.3	0.3
Kicker pulse flatness (%)	± 20	N/A
Rise/fall time (μ s)	0.6	N/A
flattop time (μ s)	304	N/A
Blade thickness (mm)	N/A	25
Aperture (H \times V mm)	N/A	30 \times 10
Longitudinal available space (m)	20	20

1.2 Beam transfer technical systems and separator

1.2.1 Septa

Collider Injection septa

Injection into the Collider will be done in the horizontal plane. A very thin septum is required and therefore two types are foreseen: a thick outside vacuum pulsed septum followed by a thin under vacuum septum. The operation scenario depends on the operation mode. The magnets need a flattop longer than 304 μ s but at different repetition rates:

- Z mode: cycle time of 43.4 s, with ten injections per cycle, which means one injection every 4 s
- W mode: cycle time 14.8 s, with two injections per cycle, which means one injection every 7 s
- H mode: cycle time 11.3 s, resulting in one injection every 11.3 s

Figure 10: Mechanical design concept for the Collider thick, outside vacuum injection septum.

Figure 11: Mechanical design concept for the Collider thin, under vacuum injection septum.

- $t\bar{t}$ mode: 10.4 s, resulting in one injection every 10.4 s

A flattop of $304\ \mu\text{s}$ is assumed for the calculations with a repetition rate of one pulse every 4 s. The septum parameters for both the thin and thick septum are shown in Tab. 3, while the mechanical concept designs are shown for thick and thin septum in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. To be able to use the eddy current topology for this septum, the pulse frequency must correspond to a maximum skin depth equal to one-fifth of the septum thickness (approximately 0.5 mm), which corresponds to a full sine pulse length of $57\ \mu\text{s}$. This pulse length is incompatible with the operation requirements. Therefore, the proposed topology is a direct drive, pulsed septum, that should be installed under vacuum. Direct drive topology mean the separation between the high field region and the field free region is done by the magnet conductor. The pulse width will be chosen significantly larger than the required flattop length. The final pulse shape is still to be determined, but the initial assumption uses a half sine with a third harmonic and an active filter. Of the two variants that will be needed, a thin septum and a thick septum, the latter will be installed outside the vacuum vessel and will be equipped with a thin-walled vacuum chamber inside the gap to limit the detrimental effect of the induced eddy currents on the magnetic field seen by the injected beam. The thin septum will be installed in its own vacuum vessel and powered with its own dedicated power converter. Despite their limited power dissipation, the magnets have to be cooled to

stabilise their electrical impedance, which is of importance for the shot to shot repeatability and the long-term drift. To this end, for the thin septum, thin-walled Inconel or stainless steel capillaries are planned to be brazed on the inside of the septum close to the pole faces. Its rear conductor and the conductor of the thick septum can be made of copper tubes. Since these devices are in the collider, inorganic insulation shall be used for increased (synchrotron) radiation resistance.

No remote positioning system is planned for simplification and cost reduction. In relation to the FCC beam size and apertures, if remote displacement would have to be included, the complexity of the system increases significantly due to the required displacement precision (which for the presently used technology is dominated by mechanical tolerances to 100 μm). In addition, the space needed for the integration of the devices into the beam line would increase further from the proposed design. A more economical and robust solution could be to adjust the septum position when switching between different FCC-ee modes. This could be done by moving the vacuum vessel or manually displacing the magnet inside the vacuum tank manually.

The cross section of the thin magnet is dominated by the structure needed to ensure its mechanical integrity. The magnet yoke itself will not exceed 80 mm \times 80 mm, and the entire magnet and support structure will fit into a 300 mm diameter vacuum vessel. The tank will provide space for vacuum pumps (VPIs, NEG or similar) under each vacuum vessel as well as space for its horizontal power feedthrough. Overall, it should be possible to limit the horizontal dimensions from the centre between both FCC beam lines to 500 mm from the orbiting beam centre on the other side. In the vertical plane the size can be limited to ± 0.5 m from the orbiting beam centre. Close to the magnets, a water distribution manifold with an electro-valve (which will be able to stop the water cooling system in case of loss of vacuum) should be foreseen (0.25 m \times 1.2 m \times 1.5 m).

The cross section of the thick septum is dominated by the structure to ensure its mechanical integrity. The magnet yoke itself will not exceed 100 mm \times 100 mm, and the entire magnet cross section will not exceed 600 mm (H) \times 400 mm (V).

It is planned to use one power converter per magnet. Each power converter will need 6 full height electronics racks, i.e. 0.8 m \times 4 m footprint, and 2 m tall. Additionally, space needs to be reserved for the water cooling supply and the cables connected between each power converter and the magnet. The power converter and the magnet should not be further than 100 m apart from each other.

Collider Dump septa

The septa used to send the beam to the dump from the Collider will deflect the beam in the horizontal plane. Pure DC operation mode is assumed. The principal septum parameters are shown in Tab. 4.

The proposed topology is a set of two low power DC septa, which are put electrically in series [41]. The magnet is quite sizeable, but due to the ample space for the coils, the power dissipation can be limited. The magnet is installed outside vacuum, using a 1 mm thin vacuum chamber made of stainless steel or Inconel. Despite the reduced power consumption, the magnets need to be water cooled. No remote positioning system is foreseen.

The cross section of the magnet is 700 mm \times 600 mm, see also Fig. 12. A connection box

Table 3: Principal parameters of collider injection thin and thick under vacuum septa.

Parameter	thin	thick	unit
Particle energy	45.6 to 182.5		GeV
Total available physical space on beam line	3000	7000	mm
Proposed physical length per magnet (tank)	1300	1300	mm
Number of magnets per beam	1	1	
Deflection angle per magnet	0.1	0.9	mrاد
Integrated magnetic field	0.061	0.548	T m
Magnetic field in centre of the magnet	0.061	0.122	
Septum position w.r.t. orbiting beam centre	TBD	TBD	mm
Equivalent magnetic length	1000	1000	mm
Beam stay clear area (H x V)	20×10	20×10	mm
Apparent septum thickness	2.8	10	mm
Septum conductor width	2	6	mm
Magnetic screen thickness	0.5	0.5	mm
Gap height (\perp to deflection)	16	20	mm
Gap width (in plane of deflection)	21	32	mm
flattop length	≥ 304	≥ 304	μs
Repetition time	4	4	s
Pulse width	5	5	ms
Relative integrated leak field	10^{-3}	10^{-3}	
GFR (H \times V)	TBD	TBD	mm
GFR precision	0.5	0.5	%
Nominal magnet current	0.775	8.75	kA
Number of coil turns	1	1	
Magnet inductance	2.0	2.5	μH
Power dissipation / unit	5	30	W
Water cooling flow rate (dP = ~ 5 bar)	1	≥ 5	L min^{-1}
Number of magnet units e^+/e^-	1/1	1/1	
Number of power converters e^+/e^-	1/1	1/1	

Figure 12: Side view of the mechanical design concept for the Collider dump septum.

Table 4: Principal parameters of collider dump septa.

Parameter	value	unit
Max. physical length available	20	m
Particle energy	45.5 to 182.5	GeV
Physical length per unit	2	m
Equivalent length per unit	1800	mm
Deflection angle	2×2.5	mrad
Integrated magnetic field	2×1.521	T m
Field in centre of the gap	0.845	T
Beam stay clear area (H x V)	20×10	mm
Equivalent magnetic length	2×1800	mm
Apparent septum thickness	25	mm
Gap height (\perp to deflection)	20	mm
Gap width (in plane of deflection)	26	mm
Relative integrated leak field	$\leq 10^{-3}$	
GFR (H \times V)	TBD	mm
GFR precision	TBD	%
Number of coil turns	40	
Nominal magnet current	336	A, DC
Power dissipation / unit (tt mode)	5.4	kW
Water cooling flow rate (dP = ~ 12 bar)	2×3	L min $^{-1}$
Number of units e^+/e^-	2/2	

for the electrical and hydraulic connections behind the magnet adds an additional 30 cm in the horizontal plane, 30 cm in the vertical plane and 60 cm in the longitudinal direction. It is expected that one power converter can run the 4 septa for each beam in series, so one power converter for the electron and another for positron extraction will be needed. Close to the magnets, a water distribution manifold with electro-valve should be foreseen ($0.25\text{ m} \times 1.2\text{ m} \times 1.5\text{ m}$).

The power converter of this type will need water cooling and takes up floor space of $2.5\text{ m} \times 0.9\text{ m}$, using full standard rack height.

1.2.2 EM separator

The first discussion and draft needs were presented in a dedicated meeting in 2022 [30]. As shown in Fig. 14, Electro-Magnetic Separators (EMS) are used at the entry and exit of the RF section to merge and separate the beams in opposite directions. To this end the magnetic field should be perpendicular to the electric field (see Fig. 13(a)) and the uniform profiles of both the magnetic and the electric field should overlap to avoid beam distortions.

Figure 13: Conceptual view of the electromagnetic separator showing the fringe fields (a) and the component considered (b).

A very basic concept for such an EMS was proposed for the ILC head-on studies in [33, 5]. However, for this version the overlapping of both longitudinal field profiles wasn't studied yet.

To preserve the longitudinal beam impedance as much as possible, 2 additional ground electrodes will be needed, extending from the beam entry flange to the beam exit flange at the symmetry (i.e., ground-potential) plane. During the LEP era, the electrostatic separator electrodes were cooled to deal with the impinging synchrotron radiation [27]. It should still be clarified if this will be needed for this device, since this will have an impact on the required footprint of the system.

In Tab. 5 the principal parameters of the EMS are shown. The main challenge resides in the need for the electric field to follow the magnetic end fields. A conventional approach would be to shape the magnetic end fields (using shims etc.) as well as possible in order to overlap them to the electric fields. Recent preliminary studies have shown that magnetic beam impedance screens can be used at the extremities to both guide/terminate the magnetic

Figure 14: Concept layout of the electro-magnetic separator near the RF cavities

and the electric field very effectively, allowing to be matched while using less physical space for a given equivalent length (see concept design in Fig. 13(b)).

Since the electric field has to be cancelled by the magnetic field in one direction, the resulting magnetic field is extremely low. Literature has shown that this is very difficult to achieve and significant R&D will be needed [28]. Apart from careful magnet design, the following possibilities will also have to be investigated:

- feasibility to measure the magnetic field online and include it in the current regulation loop
- use of an air-coiled dipole magnet geometry. This could be based on a concept used for the G-2 inflector septum [42]
- use of a magnet current control loop based on beam positioning monitors' signals

A similar challenge for a bending magnet is described in [15], where grading electrodes are installed at the extremities of the High Voltage (HV) electrodes. These additional electrodes are placed at an angle with respect to the longitudinal beam axis to reduce the field between the electrodes as a function of the longitudinal position, while the different electrode sets were supplied with HV via a built-in HV divider from the main electrodes. This arrangement allows a precise matching of the magnetic field with the electric field.

The expected price of these devices depends on an in-depth design study and cost optimisation.

Several design considerations will have to be taken into account:

- According to [28], the required low magnetic fields are not achievable with iron-cored magnets because of the remanent field. Additionally, problems with the BH curve accuracy of the iron core material are mentioned as well as the insufficient FEA results precision so that the traditional measure and optimization methods are not applicable.
- R&D is needed to make sure the magnetic field overlaps the electric field. The max deviation between the 2 field profiles needs to be determined beforehand.

Table 5: Principal parameters of each E-M separator module.

Parameter	Value	unit
Active length	2500	mm
Physical length (flange to flange)	4000	mm
Particle energy	120 to 182.5	GeV
Deflection angle	40	μrad
Beam acceptance (entry, exit flanges)	60	mm
GFR (H \times V)	X \times Y	mm
GFR precision	TBD	%
E and B profile overlap error	TBD	%
Magnetic field	4.9	mT
Electric field	1.46	MV m^{-1}
Electrode aperture	± 60	mm
Magnetic gap height	450	mm
Potential difference	± 87.6	kV
Magnet current	87	A
Number of coils	2	
Number of turns per coil	10	
Electrical resistance at the magnet terminals	27	$\text{m}\Omega$
Total cooling water flow (dP 6 bar)	2.3	L min^{-1}
Power dissipation	204	W
Good field region (x)	± 15	mm
Good field region (y)	± 10	mm
families/units	2 / 10	

- Before the system can be put into operation, both the longitudinal electric and the magnetic field need to be mapped to assure that the overlap is within specification. Although for the magnetic field measurement techniques are well understood, little experience exists for measuring the electric field. This can be simplified by measuring it at lower fields [25], since this electric fields are perfectly linear. Alternatively, assuming a very accurate 'as-built' model of the geometry exists, one can also purely rely on simulations.
- The separators are powered in 2 families of 10 devices. The required maximum spark (breakdown) rate should be defined. To limit the impact of 1 separator sparking, a decoupling circuit should be implemented between the individual devices. This could be done either with discrete decoupling resistors, or possibly by using resistive cabling.
- If it is needed to be able to quickly switch off device in case of a spark (breakdown of the electrical field), individual powering of the EM separators will be required. If this option is retained, one must be very careful to make sure that these individual devices are not parasitically coupled and the associated footprint of the generators/power converters would need to be increased significantly.[29]
- The segmentation requirement should be studied in relation with the impact of electric field breakdowns. Presently, 10 devices are proposed per side. In particular, it has to be ensured that, in case of a spark in one device, the reduced kick seen by the beam still is sufficient to keep the beam inside the machine aperture and no localised losses are provoked.
- Beam impedance will be important. To this end the use of additional ground electrodes, which span the full length of the tank are planned.
- The aperture between electrodes is to be chosen larger than the minimum necessary for the beam; this allows the electrodes to be located further from the beam (less synchrotron radiation as well as less impact from stray particles) to reduce the spark rate. An additional advantage of a large gap is the fact that the insulating support of the electrodes is further removed from the synchrotron light, which reduces the surface charge build-up [26].
- Due to the synchrotron light that will hit the electrode, they will potentially be heated up. It should be verified whether active electrode cooling needs to be implemented.
- To avoid charge build up on the insulating electrode supports, and possibly also the feedthrough, one should consider using resistive insulating rods. In the past, research has been done on ion implantation of alumina ceramic rods [39, 21]
- Synchrotron light masks will be needed upstream of each separator to limit the impact of this radiation on the spark rate.
- To simplify conditioning of these separators, it could be of interest having a rudimentary electrode displacement system where each electrode could be moved in the order of 10 mm. An added advantage of this could be that this system can be used later on to help tuning the electric field shape (longitudinally) to best match the magnetic field.

- The insulation concept for the HV feedthroughs needs to be determined. The presently used fluorocarbon liquid will not be acceptable, so an alternative in the form of oil, grease or other will have to be qualified. Dedicated R&D is to be planned on this subject.
- The magnet should be easily removable from the electrostatic separator. If the vacuum system requires bake-out prior to operation, the electrical connections should be removed prior to the bake-out. This can be avoided by equipping each devices with vacuum sector valves and baking them out of the machine on surface. This approach will also permit that the HV conditioning will also be done on surface.
- The power converters of the magnet as well as the HV power converters for the electrodes should not be too far from each separator to limit cabling cost and power loss in the cabling, although due to their DC nature no other technical length limiting terms have been identified.

The EM-separator itself will be maximum 4 m long (flange to flange). The width will be dominated by the yoke of the magnet around the vacuum vessel of the separator but will not exceed 1 m. Floor space for a decoupling resistor and a ground switch/HV connection box need to be reserved close to the HV feedthroughs (which extend, including HV connector, up to 1 m from the beam axis on both sides of the separator), with a footprint of each 30×80 cm.

Cooling systems will be needed for the magnet (demineralised water) and possibly the HV electrodes (using a suitable insulating liquid). For the former, a water manifold supplied from the standard demineralised cooling water circuit will be sufficient. This will take up approximately 0.5 m^2 . However, in case the cooling of the HV electrodes is required, a heat exchanger and a pump system will be needed to transfer the heat from the electrodes using the electrically insulating medium to the demineralised cooling water circuit.

The cabling necessary between the device and both power converters (high current and high voltage) is not particularly limited in length and can be up to several 100 m in length. The HV cables will be coaxial cables, using EPR (for increased radiation resistance, but with a low insulation resistance, so high leak current) or PE (low leak current but less radiation resistant) insulation.

The power converters and their controls shall be in areas shielded from radiation and sufficiently close to the separators to limit their cables length as indicated above.

The HV power generators footprint is equal to 2 (positive and negative) \times 5 standard full height electronics racks per EM separator, plus the 2 required HV switches (1 m^2), and the 4 corresponding decoupling resistors and ground switches (size per devices in the tunnel, see above). For the time being 2 families of EM separators are foreseen. Each of these sets of HV generators will supply 10 EM separators. Space for 2 of these clusters need to be allocated.

For the High Current power supplies, to power the magnet part of the EM separator, 4 standard full height electronic racks should suffice. One power converter is planned to supply the current for 1 family of EM Separators (i.e. 10).

As indicated in the previous paragraph, the total number of generators/power converters depends on the needs to be able switch off the device after a HV breakdown in the tank. If

individual powering would be needed, space needs to be allocated for 20 high current power converters and 40 HV generators.

The technical analysis of this device is described in further detail in [37].

Separator DC septa

DC septa are needed to bring the beam from one beam orbit close to the other central beam orbit. Two families of magnets (thin and thick) are planned in front of the EM separator and two families of septa magnets have to be foreseen at the exit of the RF section after the second family of EM separators. The integrated field quality of these devices is critical, since they deflect the orbiting beam. The field requirement for the Good Field Region (GFR) has to be coherent with the field precision required for the main ring elements such as the dipoles. As for the EM separator, the septa adjacent to the separators are only used in Higgs and $t\bar{t}$ modes. For these modes the number of bunches is limited, i.e. significantly less than the number of bunches in the Z mode. Due to this, no particular beam impedance measures are presently foreseen for the DC septa, allowing minimisation of the magnet gap height.

Initial investigations demonstrated that a Lambertson septum cannot be used, due to the inherent 2 plane deflection principle. A subsequently proposed low power topology variant was discarded due to the required apparent septum thickness. Finally, to reduce the required length for the integration of these devices, 3 thin single turn direct drive septa followed by 8 single turn direct drive thick septa are proposed. To achieve the permissible apparent septum thickness, these devices are installed under vacuum.

Since these devices use relatively high magnetic fields, they will also generate a not negligible amount of synchrotron radiation. For the time being, the required absorbers for this radiation have not yet been included in the designed layout but will need to be considered as experience with LEP already showed significant effects from synchrotron radiation [4]. The proposed parameters are shown in Tab. 6. The technical analysis of this device is described in further detail in [38].

1.2.3 Kickers

Injection Kickers

Although the kicker system will operate at four different energy levels, its design is based on the functional specifications required for the highest energy. These specifications are summarized in Tab. 7.

Two injection systems are foreseen: one for the electrons and one for positrons. Each system includes four kicker magnets.

For the collider injection, a ferrite-loaded lumped-inductance kicker magnet is the preferred choice. Operating at relatively low current and voltage, this design allows the use of an out-of-vacuum magnet. This choice enhances reliability, reduces costs, and simplifies maintenance, making it more favourable compared to other technologies considered during the feasibility study, such as striplines. Additionally, this magnet topology was previously implemented in LEP, where it demonstrated reliable performance in a lepton collider environment.

Each magnet is individually powered by its own generator. Two generator options are

Table 6: Principal parameters of DC septa magnets adjacent to the EM separators.

Parameter	Thin septum	Thick septum	unit
Number of units	2×3	2×8	
Particle energy	120 to 182.5		GeV
Powering	DC		
Deflection angle per unit	0.4	0.8	mrad
Active length per unit	2000	2000	mm
Physical length (flange to flange)	2300	2300	mm
Beam acceptance (entry, exit flanges)	50×12	120×12	mm^2
Magnetic field	122	243	mT
Magnetic gap height	12	12	mm
Magnet current	1162	2324	A
Electrical resistance at the magnet terminals	1.5	0.9	$\text{m}\Omega$
Cooling water flow ($dP = 6$ bar) per unit	3	7	L min^{-1}
Power dissipation	2	5	kW
Good field region (x)	40	100	mm
Good field region (y)		12	mm
GFR relative field homogeneity		10^{-4}	

Table 7: Principal parameters of Collider injection kickers.

Parameter	value	unit
Particle energy	45.6 to 182.5	GeV
Number of systems	4	
Number of magnets per system	5	
Total kick angle	0.04 and 0.06	mrad
Kick angle per magnet	0.013	mrad
Available aperture (beam stay clear)	60	mm
Element aperture	70	mm
Total available physical space on beam line	5.5	mm
Proposed physical length per magnet tank	TBD	mm
Effective length per magnet	0.7	m
Integrated magnetic field	7.7	mT m
Magnetic field in centre of the magnet	12	mT
Rise / fall time	600	ns
Rise and fall time definition	1.5 - 98.5	%
flattop length	304	μs
flattop quality	± 1.5	%
Repetition rate	0.3	Hz
Magnet generator Current	0.6	kA
Magnet generator Voltage	6	kV

possible: a Pulse Forming Network (PFN)-based pulse generator or a Marx generator, with the latter being the preferred choice as it maintains a lower voltage. To compensate for the long flattop duration, a significantly large capacitor is required, necessitating proper space allocation in the service gallery. The generator is connected to the magnet via a 250 m, $10\ \Omega$ cable. The lumped-inductance magnet operates in short-circuit mode and is highly impedance-mismatched with the transfer cable. However, this strong impedance mismatch on the magnet side can be attenuated by including a $10\ \Omega$ matching resistor on the generator side.

The space reservation of the injection kicker magnets in the tunnel for each system is 3 or 5 magnets \times 0.7 m (4 systems \times 3 or 5 magnets, Tab. 7). Each system has a sub-system of 3 and 5 magnets each located about 600 m apart. The cross-section of magnets is about $0.5\ \text{m} \times 0.5\ \text{m}$.

The cable length between each injection kicker and their generator is defined by the pulse requirements. Thus, the location of the service galleries is affected by the required cable lengths. The required cable length is 250 m of which includes the bending radius (1 m) and the handling path (15 m).

Required footprint space for one generator in service cavern/alcove is $2\ \text{m} \times 2.5\ \text{m} \times 3.5\ \text{m}$. As the Injection kickers have two locations 600 m apart, there are 5 generators for one location and 7 for the second and $16 + 16$ control racks (each $0.6\ \text{m} \times 1\ \text{m} \times 2.4\ \text{m}$) for one system with hot spares included.

All radiation-sensitive components, such as generators and controls, cannot be installed directly in the tunnel. The cables are radiation sensitive; their shielding will be required.

Dump kickers

As for the collider injection system, the dump kicker system is designed for the maximum energy of 182.5 GeV. Two systems are foreseen, with the required deflection being provided by nine magnets. The dump kicker main parameters are illustrated in Tab. 8

Given the similar pulse rise and fall time requirements compared to the injection system, a lumped-inductance topology has been selected. Additionally, harmonizing the systems across the FCC machine can lead to significant cost savings. The more relaxed flattop quality requirements make it possible to opt for a simpler generator to drive the magnets. This design consists of a primary capacitor discharge stage supplemented by droop compensation stages. Each generator is connected to its driven magnet through a 100 m long cable. The lumped-inductance magnet operates in short-circuit mode, causing reflections at the impedance-mismatched ends of the coaxial cable, which results in pulse overshoot. This mismatch can be partially compensated by incorporating a filtering circuit or a terminating resistor.

The space reservation of the dump kicker magnets in the tunnel for each system is 9 magnets \times 0.7 m (2 system \times 9 magnets, Tab. 8). The cross-section of magnets is about $0.5\ \text{m} \times 0.5\ \text{m}$.

The cable length between dump kickers and their generator is defined by the pulse requirements. Thus, the location of the service galleries is affected by the required cable lengths. The required cable length is 100 m. The bending radius (1 m) and the handling paths shall be taken into account in addition (15 m).

Required footprint space for one generator in service cavern/alcove is $2\ \text{m} \times 2\ \text{m} \times 3\ \text{m}$.

Table 8: Principal parameters of Collider dump kickers.

Parameter		unit
Particle energy	45.6 to 182.5	GeV
Number of systems	2	
Number of magnets per system	9	
Total kick angle	0.3	mrad
Kick angle per magnet	0.033	mrad
Available aperture (beam stay clear)	60	mm
Element aperture	70	mm
Total available physical space on beam line	TBD	mm
Proposed physical length per magnet tank	TBD	mm
Effective length per magnet	0.7	m
Integrated magnetic field	21	mT m
Magnetic field in centre of the magnet	30	mT
Rise / fall time	600	ns
Rise and fall time definition	TBD	%
Flattop length	304	μ s
flattop quality	± 20	%
Repetition rate	0.1	Hz
Magnet generator Current	1.7	kA
Magnet generator Voltage	17	kV

For each system with hot spares included, there are 12 generators and 39 control racks, each with dimensions of $0.6\text{ m} \times 1\text{ m} \times 2.4\text{ m}$.

All radiation-sensitive components, such as generators and controls, cannot be installed directly in the tunnel. The cables are radiation sensitive; their shielding will be required.

Kickers Controls

Depending on the retained pulse generator options, the following strategy applies:

- PFN-based with semiconductor switch: existing technology with respect to a pulse repetition rate of 0.3 Hz.
- Marx generator would be a new technology for ABT, and impact on controls to be studied.

Regardless of the pulse generator technology, the following topics require studies:

- machine protection
 - need to retrigger remaining elements/systems in case of an erratic pulse of one generator.
 - need for Abort Gap Keeper functionality

- Radiation to electronics: maximum flux and accumulated dose at the location of the controls

The LBDS-like generator is a known technology, but its reliability and Radiation-to-Electronics (R2E) aspects need further study. Since the number of generators is low, an active or hybrid fail-safe retriggering architecture (similar to the SBDS) would be ideal. This approach is preferable to a passive system, which is complex to control and analyse due to non-linear impedance and the resulting reflections.

2 Fcc-ee booster

2.1 Injection - extraction

2.1.1 Booster injection design

Figure 15: Schematic view of the FCCee complex baseline from the injector complex (near the SPS label) to the middle of the Collider [10].

The lepton beam is accelerated to 20 GeV in the high energy linac and transported from the injector complex to the collider complex PA in the injection tunnels shown as bright green on Fig. 15. The injection tunnels merge with the collider's on either side of the PA experimental straight section, approximately 600 m from the IP. This layout is symmetric around the IP and since the booster optics is also symmetric the scheme discussed below for the clockwise injection also applies for the counter-clockwise injection on the other side of the straight section.

At the junction with the collider tunnel, the present baseline features an angle of approximately 150 mrad between the injection and the booster beam lines. The precise geometry of the line has not been established yet but the present concept considers using around 10 m of dipoles for a total deflection of 125 mrad followed by a septum system totalling 25 mrad to align with the booster trajectory [7]. The design of the booster injection focuses on the booster lattice and injection elements themselves. The precise trajectory and optical matching from the injection tunnel will be addressed at a later stage and have not revealed any significant challenges so far.

The beam produced by the injector complex is composed of up to 4 bunches separated by 25 ns per batch which parameters are detailed Tab. 9. The booster accumulates the injected batches at a rate of 100 Hz and for up to several seconds. The baseline uses a fast injection scheme allowing consecutive batches to be injected between circulating ones. Therefore, the injection kicker has to provide a flattop of up to 80 ns with rise and fall time below 25 ns.

The PA is an experimental straight section with the booster ring reference trajectory continuously bent to curve outside the IP. Figure 16 shows matching sections between the

Table 9: Injected beam nominal parameters

Norm. emittance X (μm)	Norm. emittance Y (μm)	bunch length (mm)	dpp
20	2	4	1×10^{-3}

arc and straight sections and the entire straight section occupied by a regular FODO lattice with dipoles. The 2 m clearance between quadrupole and dipoles is not sufficient to introduce a fast injection scheme so the first step is to modify the lattice to open sufficient space in the layout.

Taking advantage of the low field of the dipoles in the straight section, with a bending radius twice bigger as in the arcs with 19.8 km, the present scheme removes dipoles to distribute their deflection on the nearby ones. A total of 6 dipole magnets are removed on each side of PA section and their deflection transferred to 6 other dipoles. This transfer of deflection has no effect on the reference trajectory outside each injection region and a negligible effect on the ring circumference of 28 μm . The dipoles are removed symmetrically with respect to the FODO lattice in order to minimize the impact on the optics and in particular the dispersion function. Some minor impact on the local dispersion remains, as shown around the electron injection point in Fig. 16.

Figure 16: Synoptics and Twiss functions for the booster ring along the PA straight section with the injection optics on the positron injection side and the nominal optics on the electron injection side. The synoptic shows dipole position in red and quadrupoles in black.

The second requirement of the injection scheme concerns the optical function and phase advance at the injection devices in the vertical plane. A high beta function at both the kicker and septa while preserving a phase advance close to 90° enhances the effectiveness of the kicker and maximises the separation between the circulating and the injected beams

at the septum. To achieve this goal while preserving the symmetry of the lattice around the local FODO structure two quadrupoles (`inj0` and `inj1`) and 2×11 independent power supplies for existing quadrupoles have to be added. This injection optics is shown on the positron injection side of Fig. 16 and features vertical beta function of up to 250 m at the septum. The injection optics changes the phase advance and the local sextuple correction scheme but a global correction allowed to compensate both effects [11]. After the injection is completed this optics can collapse back to the nominal optics for the rest of the booster cycle, hence minimising the impact on the booster beam dynamics.

The placement of the injection elements and the threading of the injected beam through the lattice elements can be seen in the close-up of the injection region on Fig. 17. Following the injected envelope, a side-channel in the horizontal plane will need to be installed between the poles of the quadrupole 065. This seems feasible with the present quadrupole design in the grey part of the aperture, between 31.5 mm and 65 mm [17].

Figure 17: Synoptics, Twiss functions and envelopes in both planes around the clockwise injection point of the booster. Injected and circulating envelopes are defined by the $\pm 15\sigma$ beam size and the injected beam parameters.

In the vertical plane, a closed orbit bump of 10 mm at the septum is considered to bring the circulating trajectory closer to the injected one although it is only modelled as an ad hoc shift of the vertical envelope in the present concept. The inside edge of the septum is located 11.5 mm from the center of the beam pipe and the injected beam is placed closer to the blade with an envelope of ± 3 mm to be compared with the blade thickness of 5 mm and the septum vertical aperture of 10 mm. At the septum the vertical slope of the injected beam is 0.26 mrad and reduced to 86 μ rad after the quadrupole 066. Downstream, a fast kicker provides an angle of 90 μ rad

The injection optics features optimised beta function and phase advance but one may notice that the vertical beta function at the kicker remains around 100 m. This may seem counterproductive since the distance between circulating and injected beam at the septa is proportional to $\sqrt{\beta_{\text{kicker}}\beta_{\text{septa}}}$. However, in the normalised phase space it follows that an error in angle $\Delta\theta$ shifts the injected beam by $\sqrt{\beta}\Delta\theta$ as shown Fig 18. Since the 1σ envelope in the normalised phase space is $\sigma = \sqrt{\epsilon}$ with ϵ the RMS emittance the maximum allowed kick error is:

$$\Delta\theta \leq N\sqrt{\frac{\epsilon}{\beta}} \quad (3)$$

with N the amplitude in σ of the resulting injection oscillations at injection. Therefore, the reduction of the beta function at the kicker allows to relax the requirements on the kicker pulse flatness. In practice, an active damper of the injection oscillations is required but at this stage, only injection system and ring optics are considered with Eq. 3 to specify a kicker flatness limiting injection oscillations to below 1σ .

Figure 18: Representation of the normalised phase space at the booster injection and the effect of a 1σ injection kick error on the resulting emittance after filamentation.

Another source of injection offset may come from the high energy linac with up to 1σ jitter in each transverse plane [20]. Such jitter should not impact the aperture requirement at injection but will need to be damped to avoid emittance growth. Discussions with RF experts are ongoing to establish the specifications of a transverse damper system. In the longitudinal plane **to be done when the booster/linac team get back to us on this.**

Due to the two-plane scheme of the injection and the small beam sizes of the lepton beams the optics, and in particular the dispersion, in both planes will need to be matched at the injection point. The optical matching was not studied for the present concept but no show stopper was identified.

This baseline injection scheme relies on a set of hardware requirements summarised in Tab. 10, considered achievable using existing technologies. A comprehensive discussion on the hardware choices is provided in Sec. 2.2. Further investigations are needed to advance this concept towards a technical design, focusing on error analysis and their impact, as well as

the operational and performance optimisation of the scheme to maintain a reliable injection despite the various drifts that may occur.

Table 10: Summary of the booster injection scheme hardware requirements

	Kicker	Septum
Beam energy (GeV)		20
Deflection angle per system (mrad)	0.09	4.5
Maximum repetition frequency (Hz)	100	DC
Rise/Fall time (ns)	25	–
flattop time (ns)	80	–
Blade thickness (mm)	–	7
Aperture (H×V mm)	–	5×10
Longitudinal available space (m)	5.5	20

2.1.2 Booster extraction design

After injection, the booster beam is accelerated to the collider energy and extracted in the technical straight section in PB (see Fig. 15) towards the booster-to-collider beam transfer line. The structure of the circulating beam depends on the operation mode and the required filling scheme of both booster and collider as well as collective effects considerations in both synchrotrons [8]. However, the present concept is based on the most stringent requirements of a fast extraction of a full turn of 304 μ s with a rise time of the kicker system within the planned collider gap between trains of 600 ns.

Unlike the experimental sections, the PB technical straight section of the booster is physically straight and contains only quadrupoles. With the wide space available between quadrupoles there is no need to modify the layout of the line to install extraction elements. To extract both electron and positron beams a symmetric design is favourable and with the collider injection system placed on the second part of the straight section (see Sec. 1.1.1) a placement at the center was chosen. Figure 19 shows the layout along the entire straight section with the extraction scheme placed in the center and symmetrically to extract both beams towards the exit of the section. The extraction scheme is entirely in the horizontal plane with both kickers and septa imparting an horizontal deflection.

The nominal optics follows a FODO structure without dispersion and features a strong beating over a period of two cells (see Fig. 19). The large beta function and near 90° phase advance per cell already match the typical requirements of a fast extraction system. However, the optics was adjusted to relax the requirement on the kicker pulse flatness to limit the extracted beam offset to 1σ (see Eq. 3). This extraction optics uses 9 independent power supplies but no additional magnets and will be needed. The injection optics is required only for a short time before extraction, without perturbing the rest of the booster cycle.

The extraction layout is fully symmetric for electron and positron beams, with the kickers placed at the precise centre of the straight section on either side of focusing quadrupole 022 (see Fig. 20(a)). Although the present concept considers dedicated kickers to electron and

Figure 19: Synoptics and Twiss functions for the booster ring along the PB straight section with the extraction and nominal optics. The envelopes are computed using the largest equilibrium beam parameters (reached for $t\bar{t}$ -mode).

positron beams extraction this placement at the center of the straight section could allow to reuse the same kickers for the extraction of both beams.

The circulating beam is moved closer to the extraction septum using a closed-orbit bump of 10 mm, although it is presently only modelled as a shift of the reference trajectory in Fig. 20(a). The kicker system provides a total angle of 0.2 mrad to ensure the required clearance at the septum blade located upstream of the following focusing magnet. In this scheme the septum blade has a thickness of 8 mm, with its inside edge located 20 mm from the reference position of the booster beam. Downstream of the septum the extracted beam envelopes crosses the quadrupole between its pole within a side-channel that will need to be installed, similarly to the booster injection Sec. 2.1.1.

Table 11: Summary of the booster extraction scheme hardware requirements

	Kicker	Septum
Beam energy (GeV)	45.6 to 182.5	
Deflection angle per system (mrad)	0.2	2
Maximum repetition frequency (Hz)	0.3	0.3
Rise/fall time (μ s)	1.1	N/A
flattop time (μ s)	304	N/A
Blade thickness (mm)	N/A	8
Aperture (H \times V mm)	N/A	18 \times 10
Longitudinal available space (m)	15	15

The hardware requirements for this extraction scheme are summarised Tab. 11. This

concept relies on realistic hardware specifications within the reach of presently available technologies and a detailed discussion on the hardware choices can be found Sec. 2.2. Error studies and the possible consequences of various equipment failures will need to be studied in view of further developing the present concept towards a technical design. As a general remark, passive absorbers will have to be placed after the extraction kickers to protect the septum and the most exposed downstream elements in the event of failures resulting in mis-kicked bunches that could hit the booster aperture. Similarly, a system of masks installed in the transfer lines to the collider, should be envisaged to intercept particles experiencing large oscillations and to shield the aperture of the line itself and of the collider.

Figure 20: Synoptics, Twiss functions and envelopes in the horizontal plane for the booster extraction (a) and dump (b). The envelopes are computed using the largest equilibrium beam parameters (reached for $\bar{t}\bar{t}$ -mode).

2.1.3 Booster dump design

The booster transfer dump system is very similar to the collider one detailed Sec. 1.1.2. It is placed at approximately the same longitudinal location (see Fig. 19) and also extracts the beam at the entrance of the straight section towards its center. The system has to be able to rise within the minimum possible gap between trains of 600 ns and extract the entire beam at once. This requires a fast extraction scheme with a flat-top of 304 μ s and the selected implementation places both kicker and septa to deflect the beam in the horizontal plane.

Unlike for the injection or extraction schemes a dump may be required at any moment and the system must be capable of safely extracting the circulating beam within a few turns. Therefore, the concept cannot rely on a manipulation of the optics or the closed orbit before the kicker system is triggered. Hence, the optics in the extraction region is not modified and the reference position of the circulating beam remains in the center of the vacuum chamber.

The kicker system provides a slightly larger angle of 0.3 mrad than used by the extraction scheme. Further down, the septum is placed upstream of the next focusing quadrupole (see

Fig. 20(b)) to take advantage of the approximately 90° phase advance per cell and the larger beta function. At the septum the dumped beam is shifted by a total of 43 mm, which accommodates the septum blade thickness of 25 mm and its inside edge at 4 mm from the ring reference position. The septum total deflection is 5 mrad and the quadrupole downstream will need to be adapted in order to accommodate a side channel of the dumped beam.

Since the circulating beam energy continuously changes along the booster cycle, the septum powering and kicker charging have to follow the beam energy from injection at 20 GeV up to the maximum energy of 182.5 GeV. Furthermore, specialised control systems will need to be considered to trigger a dump in case any of those elements do not follow their expected voltage or current functions.

The transport line to the dump only consists of a drift tube, without dipoles or quadrupoles. Small correctors may be considered at a later stage to ensure an optimum trajectory up to the dump. With a total length of 1200 from the dump kicker to the dump, the beam naturally reaches a 1σ size of 3.5 mm and 1 mm, respectively in the horizontal and vertical planes. This beam size is computed for the smallest possible beam parameters corresponding to the design equilibrium emittance in Z-mode.

Figure 21: Dumped beam envelopes along the dump lines in the horizontal plane for three different kicker strength scenario.

As a dump system, reliability is critical and one aspect in particular must be accounted for at the earliest stage of development. The total deflection of the kicker system is typically split among several independent magnets and generators but the failure of at least one element is always possible. Therefore, the extraction and transport of the beam up to the dump with one missing kicker needs to be considered. In the present concept a total of 9 kickers are used so that the loss of one corresponds to a reduction of the overall deflection of 11%. The present concept ensures that a variation in the extraction kick of up to $\pm 20\%$ maintains the dumped envelopes at the dump location within ± 150 mm, which is considered acceptable for the size of the dump and its design. Additionally, the horizontal aperture of the septum should exceed 30 mm to accommodate a $\pm 20\%$ variation in kick strength.

The required hardware parameters for this dump scheme are summarised Tab. 12 and

Table 12: Summary of the booster dump scheme hardware requirements

	Kicker	Septum
Beam energy (GeV)	20 to 182.5	
Deflection angle per system (mrad)	0.3	5
Maximum repetition frequency (Hz)	0.3	0.3
Rise/fall time (μ s)	1.1	N/A
flattop time (μ s)	304	N/A
Blade thickness (mm)	N/A	25
Aperture (H \times V mm)	N/A	30 \times 10
Longitudinal available space (m)	20	20

a detailed discussion on the technology choice of the hardware system can be found in Sec. 2.2. In view of developing this dump concept towards a technical design a comprehensive review of the failure cases and mitigation measures as well as possible errors in both the circulating beam and the dump line will need to be done. Similar considerations as those presented in the previous section hold for the protection of the booster aperture in case of failure of the extraction elements to the dump.

2.2 Beam transfer technical systems

2.2.1 Septa

Booster Injection septa

As discussed in Sec. 2.1.1, the beam is transferred from the injector complex and injected into the booster on either side of the PA experimental straight section. The hardware requirements for the injection present concept are listed in Tab. 10. The operation mode of each system will see injection at up to 100 Hz for up to \sim 30 s, followed by \sim 30 s without beam.

For injection into the booster, several septa topologies have been studied. Due to the limited bandwidth that septa can reach, initial studies focused on DC under vacuum direct drive septa and permanent magnet septa. The former solution exposes the coil insulation to the synchrotron radiation of the accelerator and would sit in the path of a mis-steered beam. A direct drive septum is therefore not the preferred solution. Another topology which has been evaluated is the permanent magnet septum topology. This has been discarded for the following reasons:

- The required septum thickness in relation to the proposed gap height is unfavourable. With the proposed geometry the leak field would exceed the permissible limit. Further R&D in the field of permanent magnet septum technology is needed to identify a suitable topology.
- To improve the septum thickness over the gap height ratio, it could be considered to put the septum under vacuum to reduce the gap height to 15 mm. The under vacuum behaviour of the permanent magnet material, likely SmCo, needs to be investigated,

Figure 22: Simulated field map of the cross section of the Lambertson septum for booster injection.

both the vacuum outgassing rate as well as the stability over time under vacuum of the alloy.

- The ageing of the permanent magnet material in the radioactive environment of the FCC-ee is not guaranteed.

To prepare for a more robust design, a Lambertson septum design has also been evaluated. The principal parameters are shown in table 13. By using a multi-turn coil, the magnet current was reduced to around 125 A, which should simplify the power converter. Field simulation of the magnet cross section is shown in Fig. 22.

To keep the apparent septum thickness to a minimum, the coil is located outside vacuum, but the second pole, including the septum, the magnet gap and the orbiting beam area are all under vacuum, see Fig. 23(a) and the mechanical concept in Fig. 23(b).

Five septa per beam will be powered electrically in series, reducing the need for power converters. Due to the moderate current, the cables between power converter and magnets do not have to be water-cooled, simplifying the system.

The space requirement for the power converters at each injection point is expected to be limited to 6 standard racks consisting of the control electronics, slow interlocking logic, power distribution controller, and the power stage.

The space required for the integration of the magnets is based on the magnet cross section and reserves some additional space for connections and mechanical support. This margin ensures possible future modification of the geometry, integration of structural aspects and mechanical parts. The space requirement for the magnet envelope can be summarized as follows (see also Fig. 24) is 300 mm × 400 mm × 3000 mm. Additionally, 0.3 m is required between each of the 5 magnets for vacuum chamber connections, bringing the total length to 16.2 m. The technical analysis of this device is described in further detail in [36].

Booster Extraction septa

The septa used for extraction towards the collider will only extract at one energy for each operation mode and the list of requirements from the extraction design are summarised in

Figure 23: Mechanical drawing of the Lambertson septum for booster injection in a cross-section side view (a) and isometric view (b).

Table 13: Principal parameters for the booster injection under vacuum Lambertson septa.

Parameter	value	unit
Particle energy	20	GeV
Deflection angle per unit	5	mrad
Integrated magnetic field per unit	0.333	T m
Physical length per unit	3000	mm
Equivalent magnetic length	2700	mm
Beam stay clear area (H x V)	15 x 15	mm
Apparent septum thickness	5	mm
Gap height (\perp to deflection)	20	mm
Pole width (in plane of deflection)	110	mm
Orbiting beam aperture	60	mm
Pulse length	DC	
Relative integrated leak field	$\leq 10^{-3}$	
GFR (H x V)	TBD	mm
GFR precision	0.1	%
Number of coil turns	20	
Nominal magnet current	123	A
Electrical resistance magnet	375	m Ω
Electrical inductance magnet	1.8	mH
Relative flattop stability	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	
Power dissipation / unit	3.7	kW
Water cooling flow rate (dP = ~ 5 bar)	4	L min $^{-1}$
Number of units e^+/e^-	5/5	

Figure 24: Mechanical concept Booster injection Lambertson septum

Tab. 11. The leak field of the septum is less critical than for the collider injection septa since they only have to be powered at extraction and are not required to track the beam energy like the booster dump septa. This opens the possibility to use a pulsed device, which is less challenging with respect to thermal dissipation. Another option, that was explored to achieve a more sustainable solution, was the use of a permanent magnet. This latter option, however, would lead to an apparent septum thickness that exceeds the requirements.

The present baseline consists of 2 pulsed outside vacuum septa. The pulse length is chosen to be relatively long, to allow a flat-top of $>304 \mu\text{s}$ to allow extraction of the full circulating beam as well as to provide sufficient time for eddy currents in the extraction vacuum chamber to decay, preventing the generation of lower quality field. To limit design effort and benefit from economies of scale, this magnet is chosen to be identical to the collider thick injection septum, albeit operating at a different current. To optimise the cost, the two magnets of each system are connected electrically in series. The principal magnetic parameters are shown in Tab. 14.

The mechanical concept design is shown in Fig. 25. For the pulse generator at each extraction point, 6 standard racks consisting of the controls, the power commutation stage, and the capacitor banks will be required. The required space should be close to the extraction septa, to ensure the transmission cable length is not exceeding a length on the order of 100 m.

Booster Dump septa

The booster dump septa shown in Fig. 26 are of the same design as the collider dump septa described in Sec. 1.2.1. However, the following operational differences have an impact on the final design of the booster dump septa. First, the field of the dump septa in the booster must follow the energy of the particles in the booster during the ramp, making it a ramped device rather than a purely DC-operated device. Second, the dynamic range of the booster dump septa is larger, as the device will be used across the energy range from booster injection energy level to top energy in the $t\bar{t}$ mode.

Due to the first reason, the system will include a link to the Beam Energy Tracking System. Because of the further increased dynamic range with respect to the collider dump septa, further development of the proposed low-power septa topology is needed to make

Table 14: Principal parameters of booster Extraction pulsed outside vacuum septa.

Parameter	value	unit
Max physical length	3000	mm
Equivalent magnetic length	2×1000	mm
Particle energy	45.6 to 182.5	GeV
Deflection angle	2×1	mrاد
Integrated magnetic field	2×0.608	T m
Beam stay clear area (H \times V)	10×10	mm
Apparent septum thickness	10	mm
Septum conductor thickness	6	mm
Gap height (\perp to deflection)	20	mm
Gap width (in plane of deflection)	32	mm
Pulse length (half sine)	5	ms
Repetition time	4	s
Lamination thickness	0.35	mm
Relative integrated leak field	$\leq 10^{-3}$	
Number of coil turns	1	
Nominal magnet current (peak)	9.7	kA
Electrical resistance magnet	2×0.5	m Ω
Electrical inductance magnet	2×2.5	μ H
Relative flattop stability	10^{-4}	
Power dissipation / unit	2×30	W
Number of units e^+/e^-	2/2	
Number of power converters e^+/e^-	1/1	

Figure 25: Mechanical drawing of the booster extraction septa integrated besides the circulating beam chamber.

sure the field homogeneity and leak field levels remain within specification throughout the dynamic range. The principal design parameters are shown in Tab. 15. For both extractions, the 2 septa will be powered electrically in series, i.e., 1 power converter per extraction.

Figure 26: Mechanical drawing of the booster dump septum without its vacuum chamber.

Table 15: Principal parameters of booster dump septa.

Parameter	value	unit
Max. physical length available	20	m
Particle energy	20 to 182.5	GeV
Physical length per unit	2	m
Equivalent length per unit	1800	mm
Deflection angle	2×2.5	mrad
Integrated magnetic field	2×1.521	T m
Field in centre of the gap at top energy	0.845	T
Beam stay clear area (H \times V)	20×10	mm
Equivalent magnetic length	2×1800	mm
Apparent septum thickness	25	mm
Gap height (\perp to deflection)	20	mm
Gap width (in plane of deflection)	26	mm
Relative integrated leak field	$\leq 10^{-3}$	
Number of coil turns	40	
Nominal magnet current	336	A, ramped
Power dissipation / unit (tt mode)	700	W
Water cooling flow rate (dP 12 bar) per magnet	2×3	l/min
Number of units e^+/e^-	2/2	

Table 16: Principal parameters of booster injection kickers.

Parameter		unit
Particle energy	20	GeV
Number of systems	2	
Number of magnets per system	1	
Total kick angle	0.09	mrad
Kick angle per magnet	0.09	mrad
Available aperture (beam stay clear)	60	mm
Element aperture	30	mm
Effective length per magnet	1	m
Integrated magnetic field	3	mT m
Integrated electric field	0.9	MV
Magnetic field on-axis	3	mT
Rise / fall time	25	ns
Rise and fall time definition	0.7 to 99.3	%
flattop length	0.08	μ s
flattop quality	± 0.7	%
Repetition rate	100	Hz
Magnet generator Current	0.26	kA
Magnet generator Voltage	± 13.4	kV

2.2.2 Kickers

Injection kickers

A stripline design has been chosen for the injection kicker system to meet the scheme requirements listed in Tab. 10 and in particular the fast rise and fall times of 25 ns. Two systems are used, each consisting of a single device and Tab. 16 lists its main parameters.

To meet the field homogeneity requirements, the stripline must be carefully designed. Numerical field simulations were carried out comparing several cross sections, finally resulting in a half-moon shaped electrode design offering the best field homogeneity parameters (see Fig. ??). To minimise the stripline's impact on the circulating beam, it is essential to achieve the desired characteristic impedance in the even-mode while maintaining the odd-mode characteristic impedance as close as possible to 50Ω to ensure the required field quality. In the odd-mode, when the kicker is active, the two conductors carry opposite voltages and the characteristic impedance significantly influences the pulse parameters. Proper impedance matching in the odd-mode is crucial to ensure optimal flattop ripple quality and rise time. In the even-mode, when the kicker is off, the impedance of the electrodes, as seen by the circulating bunches, determines the induced voltages. Any mismatch between the even-mode stripline impedance and its termination can excite resonances, which are particularly undesirable. However, it is not feasible to match both impedances to the same value in a single stripline [9].

Further optimisation studies on impedance matching will be conducted, such as considering a termination network on the load side of the stripline. This termination method also

requires a resistor between the electrodes, which presents some challenges. An in-vacuum design is difficult to implement due to concerns about power losses and vacuum compatibility, whereas an outside-vacuum design would be prone to parasitic inductance. In addition, mechanical design optimisation studies should commence soon to ensure the design is capable of withstanding synchrotron radiation.

For the generator side, the short flattop duration of 80 ns allows for the use of either an inductive adder or very short Pulse Forming Lines (PFL). Separate generators deliver both positive and negative driving pulses to the stripline via $50\ \Omega$ coaxial cables.

The PFL solution was initially favoured due to cost-performance considerations and was designed to be combined with a fast solid-state switch, such as the recently developed impact ionization mode switching of thyristors [14]. However, the significant impact of cable frequency-dependent attenuation on pulse quality led to the selection of the inductive adder as the most suitable generator choice. Pulse distortion can be compensated by an analogue modulation layer in the inductive adder [23]. In addition, the length of the cable connecting the generator to the magnet is limited to 30 m to achieve the required flattop quality.

The space reservation of the injection stripline kicker magnet in the tunnel is for each system (2 system \times 1 magnet, table 16) of 1 meter length and an envelope of 1×1 meter. The start location relative to the interaction point (IP) is at 693.3 m and the end location relative to IP is at 697.8 m.

The cable length between each injection kicker and their generator is defined by the pulse requirements. Thus, the location of the service galleries is affected by the required cable lengths. For the stripline injection kickers, the required cable length is only 30 m, which includes the bending radius (1 m) and the handling path (15 m).

Required footprint space for one generator in service cavern/alcove is $2\text{ m} \times 2\text{ m} \times 2\text{ m}$. For each system with hot spares included, there are 2 generators and 7 control racks (each $0.6\text{ m} \times 1\text{ m} \times 2.4\text{ m}$).

All radiation-sensitive components, including generators, controls, and cables, must be installed outside the collider tunnel or appropriately shielded.

Extraction kickers

The extraction of electron and positron beams from the booster is achieved through two systems, each consisting of 14 kicker magnets and following the extraction scheme requirements listed in Tab. 11. These systems employ the same lumped inductance topology used for collider injection and dump kickers, leveraging the benefits of economies of scale. Each magnet could either be driven by a pulse forming network or a Marx generator and is operated in short-circuit mode. The Marx generator consists of a main high-voltage stage and a low-voltage stage. Both stages are composed of multiple units: the stages in the high-voltage section are triggered throughout the full pulse duration, while the low-voltage stages are triggered sequentially to compensate for voltage droop along the pulse. To address the mismatch between the magnet and the transfer cable, a matching resistor can be included on the generator side. In order to provide the required flattop quality, the length of the cable connecting the magnet to the generator is limited to 100 m. The main parameters of the baseline solution for this kicker system are listed Tab. 17.

The space reservation of the extraction kicker magnets in the tunnel for each system is

Table 17: Principal parameters of booster extraction kickers.

Parameter		unit
Particle energy	45 to 182.5	GeV
Number of systems	2	
Number of magnets per system	14	
Total kick angle	0.2	mrad
Kick angle per magnet	0.014	mrad
Available aperture (beam stay clear)	60	mm
Element aperture	70	mm
Total available physical space on beam line	TBD	mm
Proposed physical length per magnet tank	TBD	mm
Effective length per magnet	0.7	m
Integrated magnetic field	8.68	mT m
Magnetic field in centre of the magnet	12.4	mT
Rise / fall time	600	ns
Rise and fall time definition	0.6 to 99.4	%
flattop length	304	μ s
flattop quality	± 0.6	%
Repetition rate	0.3	Hz
Magnet generator Current	0.7	kA
Magnet generator Voltage	7	kV

14 magnets \times 0.7 m length (2 system \times 14 magnet, Tab. 17). The cross-section of magnets is about 0.5 m \times 0.5 m.

The cable length between each extraction kicker and their generator is defined by the pulse requirements. Thus, the location of the service galleries is affected by the required cable lengths. The required cable length is 100 m which includes the bending radius (1 m) and the handling path (15 m). Required footprint space for one generator in service cavern/alcove is 7 m \times 2 m \times 3 m. For each system with hot spares included, there are 18 generators and 39 control racks (each 0.6 m \times 1 m \times 2.4 m). All radiation-sensitive components, including generators, controls, and cables, must be installed outside the collider tunnel or appropriately shielded.

Dump kickers

The booster beam dump system will be very similar to the collider dump (see Sec. 1.2.3), only requiring adjustments for placement and control. The same magnet modules and generator topologies will be used. Compared to the collider dump, which operates at a fixed energy, beam energy tracking is required. This feature can be achieved using commercially available power supplies.

The space reservation of the dump kicker magnets in the tunnel for each system is 9 magnets \times 0.7 m length (2 system \times 9 magnet, Tab. 18). The cross-section of magnets is about 0.5 \times 0.5 meters.

Table 18: Principal parameters of booster dump kickers.

Parameter		unit
Particle energy	20 to 182.5	GeV
Number of systems	2	
Number of magnets per system	9	
Total kick angle	0.3	mrad
Kick angle per magnet	0.033	mrad
Available aperture (beam stay clear)	60	mm
Element aperture	70	mm
Total available physical space on beam line	TBD	mm
Proposed physical length per magnet tank	TBD	mm
Effective length per magnet	0.7	m
Integrated magnetic field	21	mT m
Magnetic field in centre of the magnet	30	mT
Rise / fall time	600	ns
Rise and fall time definition	TBD	%
flattop length	304	μ s
flattop quality	± 20	%
Repetition rate	1	Hz
Magnet generator Current	1.7	kA
Magnet generator Voltage	17	kV

The cable length between each dump kicker and their generator is defined by the pulse requirements. Thus, the location of the service galleries is affected by the required cable lengths. The required cable length is 100 m of which includes the bending radius (1 m) and the handling path (15 m).

The required footprint space for one generator in the service cavern/alcove is 2 m \times 2 m \times 3 m. For each system with hot spares included, there are 12 generators and 39 control racks (each 0.6 m \times 1 m \times 2.4 m).

All radiation-sensitive components, such as generators and controls, cannot be installed directly in the tunnel. The cables are radiation sensitive; their shielding will be required.

Kickers Controls

An inductive adder pulse generator (IA) is a new technology for CERN, whose impact on controls must be thoroughly studied. By 2028, an IA will be deployed as part of the KFA4 CONS project, which will cover most of the required studies and implementation efforts. The 100 Hz repetition rate introduces a significant challenge for software-based controls, as the limited time available for analysis tasks, such as post-operational checks, must be addressed. Additionally, considerations related to Radiation to Electronics (R2E), including high-energy hadron (HEH) flux and maximum accumulated radiation dose at the controls' location, need to be carefully evaluated.

A Marx generator, another novel technology for CERN, also requires a detailed study

of its impact on controls. Potential synergies with the collider injection system could be exploited to optimize the design and implementation of control systems, providing efficiencies across related systems.

For the dump kickers, a generator similar to the LBDS design will be used. While this is a known and reliable technology, both reliability and R2E aspects still need to be studied in detail. Given the low number of required generators, an active or hybrid fail-safe retriggering architecture, similar to that used in the SBDS system, would be ideal. This approach avoids the complexities of a passive architecture, which can be difficult to control and analyse due to nonlinear impedance and resulting signal reflections.

Figure 27: Lepton transfer lines from the injector complex on the surface to the collider tunnel.

3 Fcc-ee injector

3.1 Transfer Lines from High Energy Linac to Booster

3.1.1 Bunch compressor

3.1.2 Transfer line geometry

The transfer line geometry has changed between MTR and this report significantly. The transfer lines at the MTR stage were passing by close to the SPS to allow for synergy with hadron transfer lines for FCC-hh and for physics program in the SPS. The design suggested here provides a direct connection from the output of the HE-linac at surface on CERN Preveessin site, see P1 in Fig.27, to the two extremities of the collider tunnel straight section of PA, see P8 and P10, respectively. This design is driven mostly by CE constraints related to scheduling and shaft availability. It also features a symmetric line design for electrons and positrons, keeping the beam dynamics impact of synchrotron radiation in the final bending sections equal for both species. The location of the injector complex allows to have a very efficient connection between HE-linac and the CERN North Area, see beamlines close to P2 in Fig.27. It remains to be discussed if a beam transfer in the reverse direction from booster back to eg NA or a direct line from HE-linac to SPS is required to design the transfer lines accordingly.

Figure 28: Xsuite survey output and reference trajectory provided by Civil Engineering. The colour bar shows the local roll angle ψ_{MADX} , which is necessary to maintain a constant vertical slope in the global frame.

3.2 Cell design and beam dynamics

As shown in Fig.27, the high energy linac to booster transport has been designed with a constant negative vertical slope of -3° in the CERN Coordinate System (CSS), combined with horizontal bending in sectors P2-P3, P4-P5, P7-P8 and P9-P10. The slope will be applied and removed at the first and last cells of the line, respectively. To maintain it along the line, the local bending plane must be progressively tilted following the expressions described in [19]. Figure 28 confirms that such a procedure yields the correct beam trajectory. This *twisting reference frame* will introduce a coupling between horizontal and vertical motion. Skew quadrupoles may be needed to control such a coupling, although they have not been included in this initial iteration.

Additionally, the beam transport from the high energy linac to the booster must be designed so as to stay within the "beam quality" budget specified in Tab. 19, which will drive the lattice design choices.

Table 19: Summary of Sector Parameters.

Sector	Bunch len. (mm)	RMS dp/p (10^{-3})	$\epsilon_{x,N}$ (μm)	$\epsilon_{y,N}$ (μm)
(...)				
HE Linac	1	7.5	16	1.6
E. Compressor	4	1.0	16	1.6
Transfer	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
Booster Inj.	4	1	20	2
(...)				

FODO cells have been chosen to design the transfer line due to their simplicity. Later iterations may explore other types of cells, which explicitly aim at minimising the impact

of synchrotron radiation (such as Theoretical-Minimum-Emittance cells). The chosen phase advance is 135 deg as it is close to the optimum for minimising emittance blow-up [40], while remaining an easy number to work with when designing orthogonal correction schemes. Figure 29 shows the horizontal emittance blow-up as a function of the cell length and the dipole fill factor for the sectors P2-to-P3¹ and P6-to-P7 (or equivalently P9-to-P10). The required quadrupole gradients, bending fields and apertures are also shown. The required aperture has been calculated with the formula:

$$A_{x,y} = n_\sigma * \sqrt{\beta_{x,y} * \frac{\epsilon_{norm,x,y}}{\gamma}} + D_{x,y} * (2 * \frac{\delta_p}{p} + \delta_{jitter}) + traj * \sqrt{\frac{\beta_{x,y}}{\beta_{max}}} + align \quad (4)$$

where $n_\sigma = 6$, $\epsilon_{norm,x/y} = 20/2 \mu\text{m}$, the 1σ momentum spread $\frac{\delta_p}{p}$ is 0.1% ($\pm 2 \sigma$ taken into account and dispersion contribution conservatively added linearly). The trajectory variation is assumed to be $\pm 2 \text{mm}$ at the locations of maximum betatron functions, the momentum jitter δ_{jitter} is assumed to be a maximum of $\pm 0.3 \%$, and there are $\pm 2 \text{mm}$ taken into account for alignment errors.

Figure 29: Horizontal emittance blow-up, bending field, quadrupole gradient and aperture as a function of cell half length and dipole fill factor.

Based on the parametric scans above, two cells have been chosen to build the line: a long FODO for the shared part of the transport (P1-to-P6) and a short FODO for the separate parts of the transport (P6-to-P8, P6-to-P10). The latter is required due to the tight bending radius of $R = 300 \text{ m}$, which leads to significant synchrotron radiation. Table 20 lists the parameters for each FODO cell. The 135 deg phase advance is close to the optimum for minimising emittance blow-up [40], while remaining an easy number to work with when designing orthogonal correction schemes.

¹P4-to-P5 has very similar behaviour to P2-to-P3.

Table 20: FODO cell parameters.

Attribute	long FODO (P1-to-P6)	short FODO (P6-to-P8/P10)
Cell length (m)	50	18
Dipole fill factor	0.5	0.67
Dipole field (mT)	130	330
Dipole length (m)	6	6
Dipoles per half cell	2	1
Quadrupole length (m)	1	1
Quadrupole gradient (T/m)	5	14
Cell phase advance (deg)	135	135

The schematics and optics functions for both cell configurations are shown in Fig. 30. The number of magnets required has been documented in [6]. For the beginning and end of the line, the bending magnets will bend vertically to introduce (and then remove) the -3 deg slope present along the entire line to descend from the HE-LINAC to the collider tunnel. In those cells, the dispersion will be vertical but similar in amplitude and shape to the one shown in Fig. 30.

Figure 30: Magnet layout and optics for long and short FODOs (quads in orange and dipoles in blue). Only horizontal dispersion is shown, but a similar vertical dispersion is expected for the cells where the -3 deg. vertical slope is applied.

Under such a configuration, tracking simulations show that both the dp/p blow-up and the bunch length increase remain under 5%. However, further investigations might be needed when including matching sections and errors, which have not been considered in this report.

3.2.1 Magnet technology and technical infrastructure needs

The magnet system of these transfer lines is specified in Table 21. The constant transfer energy of 20 GeV opens the door to permanent magnet technology, thus both technologies, electro- and permanent magnets were studied and documented in [35]. It can be concluded that both magnet technologies are technically feasible. The installation and running cost for the permanent magnet option is well below the lines with electromagnets. The technical infrastructure needs are also much reduced, however the transfer lines as whole contribute less than 10% of the injector complex power requirements. The total power requirements of the transfer lines amount to about 2 MW, compared to about 25 MW for the full injector complex. The permanent magnet option would require about a factor 10 less power for eg. corrector magnets and ventilation. The main aspect to decide between the magnet technologies comes from the operational flexibility. In case of beam stability issues in the booster, a transfer energy increase can be beneficial. On the other hand if the booster could accept a lower energy beam at injection, reducing the transfer energy reduces the power consumption of the full injector complex which is driven by the HE-linac. The main field of permanent magnets can be tuned by about $\pm 20\%$ by increasing or decreasing a leakage field via mechanical shunts. The shunt modification and subsequent magnetic field measurement requires several weeks. Another argument for operational flexibility is the duty cycle of the injector complex which varies between 5 and 75% depending on the operation mode. In particular in the low duty modes, the injector beam can be used for experiments beyond FCC physics and shot-to-shot variability of beam parameters including the transfer energy open the door to a very diverse physics program as discussed in [16]. At this stage, electromagnets are chosen as baseline technology due to the higher operational flexibility for FCC and any science program beyond FCC.

Table 21: Summary of magnet specifications, assuming polarity switching and the FODO parameters from Table 20. For ease of manufacturing and costing, the 6 m dipoles have been split into 1 m segments. The number of dipoles quoted refers to the number of 1 m segments.

	Unit	Quadrupoles	Dipoles	Correctors
Total number		338	286x6=1716	224
# magnets in common line		162	192x6=1152	108
Length	m	1	1	tbd
Aperture (diameter)	mm	30	30	30
Gradient	T/m	5-15	-	-
Field	mT	-	150-400	tbd
Deflection	μrad			O(10)
Field homogeneity		O(10^{-3})	O(10^{-3})	tbd
Polarity switching time	s	O(1)	O(1)	

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